

Triethylamine Oxide and Iron(II) as Initiator of Methylmethacrylate Polymerization

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Triethylamine-oxide-Fe²⁺ redox system has been found to be an efficient initiator of aqueous polymerization of methylmethacrylate. Its mechanism has been found to be basically similar to the electron transfer mechanism of H₂O₂-Fe²⁺ or N-haloamine-Fe²⁺ as initiator. This system incorporates only the amino end group (no hydroxyl) into the polymer to an extent of about one group per polymer molecule. A large portion of the total amino groups introduced into the polymer are quaternary in nature. This initiator system proves to be useful for the preparation of polymers containing amino groups at one end only.

THE demethylation reaction of N-amine oxide is known to proceed via free-radical intermediate^{1,2}. The reaction may be caused by reducing metal salts e.g., Fe²⁺, Cr²⁺, V²⁺, Ti²⁺ etc. in acidic medium.

The present study has been undertaken to examine the possibility of such systems as polymerization initiators in aqueous medium and to analyse the end groups of the resultant polymers by recently modified dye partition (extrapolation) method of Mandal and Palit^{3,4} in order to elucidate the mechanism of the reaction.

Experimental

Methyl methacrylate (MMA), methyl acrylate, and acrylonitrile were purified by distillation under reduced pressure⁵.

Triethylamine was treated with KOH beads and distilled. FeSO₄·(NH₄)₂SO₄·6H₂O was used without further purification.

Aqueous polymerization of MMA was carried out at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere in the dark. Triethylamine oxide was prepared as discussed in the literature^{6,7}. A 22.5 ml. (0.20 mole) of 30% H₂O₂ was added with cooling to a solution of 0.10 mole of triethylamine and the resulting solution was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature with occasional warming. The method of Cope *et al.*^{8,9} for following the disappearance of amine and for decomposing the excess H₂O₂ has been followed. The required pH of the reaction mixture was achieved by adding sulfuric acid. The isolated polymers were washed with water and dried. The basic groups in the polymers were converted to salts by precipitating the benzene solution twice in acidified methanol⁴. Acid is omitted in the final precipitation step.

The number of average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) of the polymer samples was determined osmotically in tetrahydrofuran (THF) using a Hewlett-Packard 501 high speed membrane osmometer (08 membrane).

The dye partition (extrapolation) method of Mandal and Palit³ was used for amino end group determination^{3,4}.

Results and Discussion

Triethylamine-oxide itself does not initiate polymerization in dark at room temperature, but act as a retarder for some vinyl polymerization¹⁰. However, in the presence of Fe²⁺, it induces polymerization without any induction period. Table-1 summarizes the results of MMA polymerization obtained with triethylamine oxide-Fe²⁺ initiator system. The requirement of Fe²⁺ seems to be critical, concentration less than about 5x10⁻³ mol.l.⁻¹ does not constitute an efficient initiating system. A concentration as high as 1.5x10⁻² mol.l.⁻¹ seems to effect a little lowering of the polymer yield. The concentration of triethylamine-oxide suitable for polymer preparation lies in the range 10⁻³-10⁻² mol.l.⁻¹. The number of average molecular weights (\bar{M}_n) of the polymers prepared with this initiator system are relatively low (ca. 10⁴-10⁵).

Free-radical nature of the polymerization is clearly evident from the fact that polymerization is inhibited in presence of conventional free radical scavengers viz., diphenylpicrylhydrazyl, hydroquinone, *p*-benzoquinone etc., and retarded effectively by atmospheric oxygen and the plot of 1/ \bar{M}_n against the square-root of the initiator concentration (triethylamine-oxide) at a fixed concentration of Fe²⁺ and MMA is linear (Figure-1).

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TABLE-1. RESULTS OF THE POLYMERIZATION OF METHYL METHACRYLATE (MMA) IN AN AQUEOUS SYSTEM.
 INITIATOR : TRIETHYLAMINE-OXIDE + Fe²⁺. [MMA] = 9.4 × 10⁻³ mol. l.⁻¹; pH : 3.50;
 N₂ ATMOSPHERE ; IN DARK AT ≈ 30°C.

Sample No.	[(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ NO] × 10 ³ mol. l. ⁻¹	[Fe ²⁺] × 10 ³ mol. l. ⁻¹	Time of polymerization in hours	% yield	$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-4}$	Number of Amino end groups per polymer molecule		
						Quaternary	Others	Total
1	1.02*	0.10	48	0	—	—	—	—
2	1.02*	1.00	48	0	—	—	—	—
3	1.02	10.00	3½	77.9	25.01	0.61	0.31	0.92
4	5.10*	1.00	48	0	—	—	—	—
5	5.10	5.00	3	53.6	10.23	0.70	0.35	1.05
6	5.10	10.00	3	76.1	8.18	0.65	0.33	0.98
7	5.10	20.00	1½	69.2	9.23	0.76	0.36	1.12
8	10.20*	0.10	48	0	—	—	—	—
9	10.20*	1.00	48	0	—	—	—	—
10	10.20	5.00	1½	36.2	7.91	0.59	0.29	0.88
11	10.20	10.00	1½	68.0	5.35	0.66	0.34	1.00
12	10.20	15.00	1½	60.0	6.24	0.70	0.35	1.05

* No polymerization takes place.

Figure-1. Plot of reciprocal of number average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) against square root of triethylamine oxide concentration (in mol. l.⁻¹).
 [Fe²⁺] = 1 × 10⁻³ mol. l.⁻¹ and
 [MMA] = 9.4 × 10⁻³ mol. l.⁻¹.

The analysis of the polymers reveals that they possess only amino end groups to an extent of about

one group per polymer molecule. A large fraction (≈ 66%) of the amino groups is quaternary in nature. These polymers contain no hydroxyl end groups as determined by dye-partition technique^{3,11}. The failure to detect hydroxyl end groups in such polymers is probably due to the scavenging of hydroxyl (OH) radicals by tertiary amine oxide or radicals derived from them¹¹. From these results the following mechanism of primary radical generation is suggested :

Primary radicals produced in the reaction (i) incorporate a quaternary ammonium group in the polymers, whereas those produced in (ii) incorporate tertiary amine groups. It can be mentioned here that this mechanism is basically similar to the electron transfer mechanism of H₂O₂-Fe²⁺ and N-haloamine-Fe²⁺ as initiator of vinyl polymerization^{4,12}.

Ferris *et al*¹ suggested a similar reaction with trimethylamine oxide and Fe²⁺ in acidic medium.

Regarding the termination of poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) radicals by ferric salts it has been established that PMMA radicals are not terminated by Fe³⁺ and/or FeOH²⁺ in aqueous media¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Furthermore, incorporation of on average only one end group per polymer molecule rules out both the primary radical termination or, termination by mutual combination. Thus, it seems that here chain termination takes place predominantly through disproportionation of the growing polymer radicals. Incorporation of on average 1 end group per polymer molecule in case of aqueous polymerization of methyl methacrylate for various initiating systems was also realized by several workers^{4,13,17,18} where it seems that chain termination of PMMA radicals takes place most predominantly through disproportionation. These results are in contrast to the claim that in aqueous heterophase polymerization, which mechanistically approaches emulsion polymerization, the termination of polymer radicals (here PMMA radicals), in the particle phase is effected predominantly by primary radicals and should incorporate on average 2 end group per polymer molecule¹¹. Thus, it seems from this study that the accepted mechanism of termination by disproportionation for PMMA radical (based mostly on end group analysis of PMMA prepared in homogeneous non-aqueous media using dissociative initiator) is also true in case of aqueous heterophases polymerization of methyl methacrylate.

Although triethylamine oxide-Fe²⁺ is an initiator for MMA polymerization, no polymerization of acrylonitrile, methylacrylate and acrylamide occur with this initiator.

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